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MANAGING FATIGUE FOR ELITE SPORTSPERSONS – RESTING AND REJUVENATION OF THE BODY & MIND

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Abstract. In this work, we propose techniques and methods for managing fatigue in elite sportspersons. We consider such techniques as Visualization, Sound Sleep and Monitoring of Training Load. We also consider the importance of rest for the sportsman's nervous system and body. And, in the final part of our research, we make general recommendations for athletes on how they can improve their mental state by using modern technologies and methods such as Time-motion analysis (TMA), Global Positioning System (GPS) tracking, Digital video and Heart Rate Monitoring.

Keywords: fatigue, mental preparation, training load monitoring.

Introduction. Over a period of the last 3 to 4 decades, Sports has evolved into a full-time career for several Elite Sportspersons. With many Athletes exposed to high training loads and high training and competition stress, it is necessary to manage risks associated with the resultant Fatigue possibly leading to diminished Performances, injuries & illnesses [1].

However, with improved Monitoring Techniques and better knowledge of Human Physiology/Biochemistry, we have seen several high profile Athletes maintaining Peak performance over an extended Sporting life such as Rafael Nadal, Michel Phelps, Cristiano Ronaldo, Serena Williams, Steffi Graf, Sachin Tendulkar, Svetlana Khorkina, Roger Federer, Carl Lewis and many more who have successfully warded off resultant fatigue in spite of Playing Sport at the highest level and maintained very high standards of Performance & Professionalism.

In this paper, we consider different techniques and methods for managing fatigue in elite sportspersons. Special attention is paid to mental techniques and Monitoring of Training Load.

Objective: The main goal of this paper is to explain to coaches and sportsmen how they can manage fatigue using different mental techniques and Monitoring of Training Load in order to achieve high sporting results on a consistent basis.

Results of the research. We propose 3 techniques for managing fatigue in elite sportspersons: Visualization, Sound Sleep and Monitoring of Training Load.

Visualization: It creates a blueprint in mind with a rehearsal by repeating mental practice. Movement is automatic and easy to recall. Visualization works as it produces small muscle contractions as if you are actually playing the sport.

If we rehearse often and with intensity, we strengthen the muscle firing; so, the same is recalled efficiently during competition. It creates muscle memory similar to the actual practice on a field which is apparent when some young boys and girls excel in some sports when they watch the game with a lot of interest in various Media.

It helps in at least 3 ways:

- Assists in reducing actual practice time on the ground thus conserving body & managing fatigue.
- Correct errors during visualization thus learning faster on the ground.
- Improves longevity in sports and minimizes burnout due to improved utilization of resources.

Elite Athletes will always strive to improve their performance during Events which may result in an increase in the frequency, duration and intensity of Training. Coaches & Athletes will have to manage varying Loads during the Competition & Post competition phases which will result in varying degrees of Fatigue.

Striving to improve Sporting Techniques and prolonged Training sessions to improve the Technical ability of an Athlete must cease a few days prior to the event.

Immediately prior to the event, carry out a lot of Visualization and Mental Preparation with fitness and warm-up thrown in so the Athlete is mentally & physically absolutely Ready to face the challenge of the Event.

It is vital that Athletes and Coaches focus on Training consistently throughout the year with weekly Breaks and occasional Long breaks away from the competition.

As the Athletes' Bodies get stronger with time/age and the fitness regime they follow, they are naturally able to take increased Training Loads with longer duration, more frequency, and increased intensity. This must be taken into account while charting out Training schedules for the future.

Also, Senior Elite Athletes – aged 30 years and above and in certain Sports like Gymnastics, even aged 25 & more, may plan for reduced Training Loads in order to continue to enjoy Sport at the highest level and manage Body resources as they have developed Peak Technical ability and Muscle memory by that age. For them, it's vital to manage Body resources in order to prevent injury/breakdowns.

It is important to have a Coach who understands her Trainee and her body well. A Good Coach can usually pick the cues of Fatigue faster than the Athlete himself – A Coach can advise that you are not leaning forward as you used to, your Steps are too heavy or your steps are falling a bit short. These are all signs of Fatigue.

That is when you need to take time off and do some Mental Practice off the Sporting Arena / Track. A bit of Cross Training in a different Sport – Table tennis, Volleyball, or Biking will definitely help to take Focus away from your own Game for a short while and come back Afresh to your core Game with renewed Vigor and Relaxation. That is when you practice on the Mental side of Training and provide a Rest on the Physical Aspects. If left unchecked, Fatigue leads to a diminished mental attitude and a desire to quit.

When you train for Soccer – Matches are 90 Minutes duration. But once in a while, you can have a situation where you are 2 - 2 tied up after a hard-fought game. And it's a Knock - out Match or for that matter at 2 - 2 sets each in a 5 Setter Tennis Match. At this point, you have exhausted your physical and mental energy – and you hit the proverbial wall. It is a matter of how you respond to the Wall that separates the Winners from the rest of the Pack. If you can visualize the Wall – that feeling of Fatigue before it happens, you can plan ahead and work on a different outcome. It is not only about the Technical ability at this point in the game. Physically

and Mentally, the ability to stay in the Match takes over. Peak Fitness levels for Athletes are an absolute necessity at this stage in a Match. The Wall is as much Physical as it is Mental. Practice hitting it before you get there during Practice sessions.

Sound Sleep as a weapon against Fatigue

Sound and deep sleep are important components to tackle fatigue for Athletes. Anxiety, adrenaline & a worried mind will disturb your sleep. The key to sound sleep is to surrender and not to try harder. When in Bed, Focus on your breath & clear your mind.

Make sure that there is no Lights & Loud music around which can disturb sleep.

Avoid Tea / Coffee two to three hours before Bed.

If at all you get up in the Night, do not Panic – Do not get up from Bed / Turn On Lights / Check your Mobile. Breathe deeply – imagine a relaxing/enjoyable scenario while still lying down.

Sound Sleep – An important component of your training schedule – for Peak Athletic Performance.

Power Nap – About 20-30 minutes before the event will do a world of good as you are absolutely fresh for the upcoming event – Physically & Mentally.

Monitoring of Training Load

Monitoring of load is implemented to try to reduce the risk of injury and illness to the Athletes. It has become an increasingly modern, scientific approach to understanding Athletes & Training responses. Once this data is available, it is possible to examine Training Load-Performance Relationships & also enable appropriate planning for Training loads, Competitions & Recovery afterward.

However, for some Athletes, insufficient resources can be a major reason for not including a system of scientific Training monitoring. Resources may be in the form of Time, money or appropriate human resources needed to collect, process, and analyze the data.

In such cases, however, the Athletes / Coaches may not lose heart. The Athlete must learn to listen to his/her body as it will give signals of fatigue and Good Coaches can always catch minor variations in Athletes' movement/behaviour patterns when fatigued either Physically or Mentally. And these Athletes with a lack of resources can do equally well as they may use this lack of Resources as a Motivational factor for smart workouts and better Technical ability. As the Performance improves, the Resources almost always become available sooner than later (with the advent of the Internet).

Variables for Monitoring Training Load

Several Variables may be used to measure Training Loads and subsequent Fatigue.

- Frequency of Sessions – Daily / Weekly / Monthly / 6 Monthly / Yearly
- Time devoted to each session
- Intensity – Maximum / Consistent
- Maximal Effort – Max Power used, Sprint speed, Jump Height
- Repeat Efforts – No of Efforts, Quality of efforts
- Illness - Reason, duration
- Injury – Type, duration
- Physiology & Biochemistry Analysis – Baseline, Response to Exercise
- Body composition – Total Body Mass, BMI, Fat Mass

- Sleep – Quantity, Quality
- Psychology – Stress, Anxiety, Motivation

Various Methods for Monitoring Training Load

In Sports, Time-motion analysis (TMA), Global Positioning System (GPS) tracking and Digital video are becoming increasingly popular to monitor Athletes during Training & Competitions.

Monitoring Heart Rate is one of the most common means of assessing Training load in Athletes. The use of heart rate monitoring during exercise is based on the relationship between heart rate and oxygen uptake. However, the percentage of maximum heart rate is often used to both prescribe and monitor intensity.

Heart-Rate Recovery (HRR) is the rate at which the heart rate declines at the completion of exercise and has been suggested to be a marker of Training status in athletes. HRR can be calculated over varying time frames, usually between 30 s to 2 min, with the difference between the end-of-exercise Heart Rate and Heart Rate at 60 s post-exercise being most commonly used.

Conclusion

Over a period of the last 3 to 4 decades, Sports has evolved into a full-time career for several Elite Sportspersons. With many Athletes exposed to high training loads and high training and competition stress, it is necessary to manage risks associated with the resultant Fatigue possibly leading to diminished Performances, injuries & illnesses.

All Work & No Relaxation creates an Over Trained Athlete.

It is extremely important to build an adequate Rest Period into your Training schedule to allow yourself to recuperate both Mentally & Physically.

It is extremely important for an Athlete to understand his/her Body and frame a Training schedule taking care of the Body Rest requirements.

It is very easy to get influenced & misled by watching other Athletes perform and trying to copy them.

It is important to sit and plan your Training Schedule with your Coach and Fitness Trainer. I usually recommend a complete day off from Training once a week so you catch up with your family and friends. They are a crucial part of the Support system for an Athlete so it's important to take some time off for them too and usually it will result in recuperating the mind and body.

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